
Interval and point estimation in adaptive phase II oncology trials with binary endpoint

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Abstract

Phase II clinical trials are concerned with making decision of whether a treatment is sufficiently efficient to worth further investigations in late large scale Phase III trials. In oncology Phase II trials, frequentist single-arm two-stage group-sequential designs with a binary endpoint are commonly used. To allow for more flexibility, adaptive versions of these designs have been proposed. In this paper we propose point and interval estimation for adaptive designs in which the second stage sample size is a pre-specified function of first stage's number of responses. Our approach is based on sample space orderings, from which we derive p -values, and point and interval estimates. Simulation studies show that our proposed methods perform better, in terms of bias and root mean square error, than the fixed-sample maximum likelihood estimator.

Keywords

Adaptive Designs, Bias, Clinical Trials, Estimation, Oncology Phase II, RMSE

1 Introduction

Phase II trials are concerned with making decision of whether a treatment is sufficiently efficient to justify its further investigations in late large scale Phase III trials. In oncology Phase II trials, frequentist single-arm two-stage group-sequential designs with binary endpoints are commonly used. Based on ethical desirability to expose less patients to an inefficient treatment and to speed-up the development process, these designs allow early termination of the trial for futility and/or efficiency (e.g., designs by¹ and²). In such designs the sample sizes and decision rules for each stage are predefined. To allow flexibility, adaptive versions of these designs have been proposed^{3–10}. Adaptive designs allow for modification of the trial at interim analysis using the trial's accumulating data and/or external information without jeopardizing trial's integrity and validity.

Although the main goal of oncology Phase II trials is hypothesis testing, estimation of the efficacy parameter after such trials remains important, specially in cases where the treatment was deemed successful since it will be needed for planning Phase III trials. In group-sequential designs (GSD), due to the possibility of early stopping for either futility or efficacy, the fixed-sample maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) of the treatment effect (response probability) is

no longer unbiased. This issue has been acknowledged by many authors, and alternative estimation methods have been proposed in the literature^{11–19}. However, most of the estimation methods for GSD are not applicable to adaptive designs. Unfortunately, the literature on estimation in adaptive GSD is mainly on Phase III clinical trials^{20–35}. To the best of our knowledge, estimation in oncology Phase II adaptive single-arm GSD with a binary endpoint has only been discussed recently by³⁶, who proposed point estimator that can be interpreted as a constrained posterior mean estimate based on the non-informative Jeffreys prior. Their method is computationally intensive, and they have implemented it in the Julia³⁷ programming language using the JuMP³⁸ package and the Julia interface³⁸ to the commercial solver Gurobi³⁹.

In this paper, we propose interval and point estimation procedure for two-stage single-arm adaptive designs with pre-specified adaptation rule. We consider designs in which the second stage's sample size is a pre-specified function of first stage's number of responses. However, some of the

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approaches that we propose can be extended to flexible designs. The procedure uses the concept of stage-wise ordering, and it is less computationally intensive and can readily be implemented in the statistical programming language R⁴⁰. We first propose and discuss different approaches for defining sample space orderings, from which we derive p -values and then interval and point estimates. We also present the results from a simulation study to evaluate the performance of the proposed methods. The paper is organized as follows. We first give an overview of the adaptive designs for which we are developing the proposed methods. Afterwards we give the methodological details of our proposals, an illustrative example, then the results of the simulation study and we end with conclusions and a discussion.

2 Adaptive phase II oncology designs

We build our methodology for two-stage adaptive phase II oncology designs with binary endpoint and a pre-specified adaptation rule, like those proposed by⁸ and⁹. These designs extend the classical binary endpoint oncology Phase II GSD by allowing the sample size of second stage to depend on the number of responses observed in the first stage. Like their classical GSD counterparts they test, at type I error rate α and type II error rate β , the null (H_0) versus the alternative (H_1) hypothesis:

$$H_0 : \pi \leq \pi_0 \text{ vs } H_1 : \pi \geq \pi_1$$

where π_0 is the maximum response rate considered to be uninteresting and π_1 is the minimum desirable response rate, with $\pi_1 > \pi_0$.

The designs we consider in this paper are defined by the first stage sample size, n_1 , futility and efficacy boundaries, l_1 and u_1 ($u_1 > l_1$), which are fixed, and the second stage sample size, $n_2(x_1)$, which depends on the number of responses observed in the first stage, x_1 . We further have the conditional error function, $D(x_1)$, and the corresponding decision boundary, $l(x_1)$, which are also functions of x_1 . At the interim analysis, the trial is stopped with acceptance of H_0 if $x_1 \leq l_1$ or with rejection of H_0 if $x_1 \geq u_1$. Otherwise the trial proceeds to the second (final) stage, after which H_0 is rejected if $p_2 < D(x_1)$ or, equivalently, $x > l(x_1)$, where p_2 is the second stage p -value and x is the total number of responses (i.e., $x = x_1 + x_2$). An example of such designs is given in Table 1.

Note that the discrete conditional error function $D(x_1)$ in Table 1 is non-decreasing in x_1 , and takes values within $[0, 1]$. We assume these two properties throughout

Table 1. ⁸'s optimal adaptive design for $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta) = (0.2, 0.4, 0.05, 0.1)$

$n_1 = 20, n_{2,max} = 39$			
x_1	$n_2(x_1)$	$D(x_1)$	$l(x_1)$
≤ 4	0	0	0
5	16	0.082	10
6	30	0.129	14
7	33	0.200	15
8	39	0.241	17
9	39	0.376	17
≥ 10	0	1	0

the paper. $D(x_1)$ defines for each possible number of responses in the first stage, $x_1 \in \{0, \dots, n_1\}$, the conditional type I error rate to be used in the second stage⁶. It is clear that in these designs the first stage decision boundaries are $l_1 = \max\{x_1 | D(x_1) = 0\} = \min\{x_1 | D(x_1) > 0\} - 1$ and $u_1 = \min\{x_1 | D(x_1) = 1\} = \max\{x_1 | D(x_1) < 1\} + 1$, and the first and second stage p -values are $p_1 = 1 - B(x_1 - 1, n_1, \pi_0)$ and $p_2 = 1 - B(x_2 - 1, n_2(x_1), \pi_0)$, where $B(x, n, \pi)$ is the binomial cumulative distribution function (c.d.f) with x successes, n trials and success probability π .

3 Classical sample space orderings

The construction of confidence intervals and p -values entails determining the probability of obtaining an outcome that is at least as extreme as the observed one and, for this, a sample space ordering is needed. For the case of one outcome variable, in fixed-sample designs, the sample space ordering is simply the ordering of the real numbers. However, in GSD the ordering is not clearly defined because, apart from the test statistic, the number of stages also plays a role when ordering the outcomes. Different sample space orderings for GSD have been suggested in the literature. The stage-wise ordering, first proposed by⁴¹ and later discussed by several other authors⁴²⁻⁴⁶, is a widely used sample space ordering in GSD. For classical GSD counterparts of the adaptive designs above, i.e., designs in which n_2 and l are also fixed, the stage-wise ordering can be defined as it follows. Let m be the stopping stage and x the total number of responses. A trial outcome (m', x') is at least as extreme (against H_0) as the observed trial outcome (m, x) , written as $(m', x') \succeq (m, x)$, if one of the following conditions is met:

- (A) $m' = m$ and $x' \geq x$
- (B) $m' = 1, m = 2$ and $x' \geq u_1$
- (C) $m' = 2, m = 1$ and $x \leq l_1$

Other suggested sample space orderings include the likelihood ratio ordering^{47–49}, sample mean ordering⁵⁰, and score test ordering⁴⁹.

For the adaptive designs the stage-wise ordering discussed here can be inconsistent with the design’s decision rule when $m' = m = 2$. For example, for the design in Table 1, $x = 11$ with $x_1 = 5$ leads to rejection of H_0 while $x = 16$ with $x_1 = 8$ does not. This follows from the nature of the conditional error function.

4 Alternative sample space orderings

To overcome this inconsistency, we propose alternative sample space orderings that take into account the conditional error function and adaptation rule. We leave the cases (B) and (C) and (A) when $m' = m = 1$ unchanged. But when both outcomes are from trials that continued to the second stage (i.e., $m' = m = 2$) we compare them taking into account their respective rejection boundaries. We accomplish this by defining a function $\delta(x_1, x_2)$ that in some way incorporates the rejection boundary of the trial outcome. Then have that $(m', x'_1, x') \succeq (m, x_1, x)$ if one of the following conditions is met:

- (A1) $m' = m = 1$ and $x' \geq x$
- (A2) $m' = m = 2$ and $\delta(x'_1, x'_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2)$
- (B) $m' = 1, m = 2$ and $x' \geq x_1$
- (C) $m' = 2, m = 1$ and $x \leq l_1$

We propose three different methods to define $\delta(x_1, x_2)$. The first two quantify the deviation between x and $l(x_1)$. In the first method we define $\delta(x_1, x_2)$ using directly x as

$$\delta(x_1, x_2) = x_1 + x_2 - l(x_1) = x - l(x_1) \quad (1)$$

and in the second we define $\delta(x_1, x_2)$ using the second stage p -value as

$$\delta(x_1, x_2) = \tilde{\delta} [x_1, p_2(x_2)] = D(x_1) - p_2(x_2) \quad (2)$$

In both methods, δ is defined such that it equals to a constant when the outcome is at the decision boundary (i.e., when $x_2 = l(x_1) - x_1$ and $p_2 = D(x_1)$). That is, $\delta [x_1, l(x_1) - x_1] = c_1$ and $\delta [x_1, D(x_1)] = c_2$. Here $c_1 = c_2 = 0$, meaning that the null hypothesis is rejected if $\delta(x_1, x_2) > 0$. The inequality $\delta(x'_1, x'_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2)$ in the case (A2) of our proposed sample space ordering can be stated as $x'_2 \geq x - l(x_1) + l(x'_1) - x'_1$ for the first method and $p'_2 \leq p_2 - D(x_1) + D(x'_1)$ for the second one.

The two ways of defining the function δ above are strictly linked to the design’s decision rules, and therefore require trials to strictly follow the design. We will see later that Method 2 yields valid p -values even if the adaptation rule is not strictly adhered to. One way to allow for flexibility is to order the outcomes using combination functions from adaptive tests. Combination functions combine the first and the second stage p -values, with the assumption that the data from the two stages are from independent cohorts of patients. An extensive discussion on adaptive combination tests can be found in⁴⁶. The idea is to define a combination function $C(p_1, p_2)$, setting $\alpha_0 = 1 - B(l_1 - 1, n_1, \pi_0)$, $\alpha_1 = 1 - B(u_1 - 1, n_1, \pi_0)$, and finding c such that type I error is controlled, i.e.,

$$\alpha_1 + \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha_0} \int_0^1 I_{[C(p_1, p_2) \leq c]} d_{p_2} d_{p_1} = \alpha$$

where $I_{[S]}$ equals to 1 if S is true and 0 otherwise.

Given the combination test, the most natural ordering on the second stage is according to $C(p_1, p_2)$, i.e., if we have performed a second stage we consider a second trial outcome with stage-wise p -values (p'_1, p'_2) as more extreme than our observed outcome if $C(p'_1, p'_2) < C(p_1, p_2)$. Even though the Phase II designs we are dealing with might not be based on a combination function C we can build an ordering based on C that is consistent with the rejection region given by the function D (or equivalently given by the function l). To this end we define the C ’s corresponding conditional error function

$$A(p_1) = \max\{y \in [0, 1] : C(p_1, p_2) \leq c\}$$

and then calculate the backwards image p_{1b} such that $A(p_{1b}) = D(x_1)$, where $D(x_1)$ is the conditional error of the original design.

A natural and common choice for $C(p_1, p_2)$ is the weighted inverse normal combination function⁵¹, which can be represented as⁴⁶

$$C(p_1, p_2) = 1 - \Phi [w_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_1) + w_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_2)],$$

where Φ is standard normal c.d.f., and w_1 and w_2 are predefined weights chosen such that $w_1^2 + w_2^2 = 1$. Here we propose to use weights that give more emphasis to the stage with higher sample size, i.e.,

$$w_1 = \sqrt{\frac{n_1}{n_1 + n_2(x_1)}} \text{ and } w_2 = \sqrt{\frac{n_2(x_1)}{n_1 + n_2(x_1)}}.$$

The conditional error function of the inverse normal combination function is

$$A(p_1) = 1 - \Phi \left[\frac{\Phi^{-1}(1-c) - w_2 \Phi^{-1}(1-p_2)}{w_1} \right].$$

Solving $A(p_{1b}) = D(x_1)$ for p_{1b} we get

$$p_{1b}(x_1) = 1 - \Phi \left\{ \frac{\Phi^{-1}(1-c) - w_2 \Phi^{-1}[1-D(x_1)]}{w_1} \right\}.$$

We, finally, define δ as

$$\delta(x_1, x_2) = \bar{\delta}[p_{1b}(x_1), p_2(x_2)] = 1 - C(p_{1b}, p_2). \quad (3)$$

With δ defined in this way, the condition $\delta(x'_1, x'_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2)$ in the case (A2) of the proposed sample space ordering becomes $C(p'_{1b}, p'_2) \leq C(p_{1b}, p_2)$, meaning that the outcome with lower $C(p_{1b}, p_2)$ is considered to be more extreme.

Another possible sample space ordering could be to simply order the trial outcomes by the proportion of responses, i.e., $(x_1 + x_2)/[n_1 + n_2(x_1)]$. However, this ordering would not always be consistent with the design's decision rule because in some designs the ratio of the final decision boundary and the total sample size, i.e., $l(x_1)/[n_1 + n_2(x_1)]$, might not be constant. For instance, in the ⁸'s design for $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta) = (0.5, 0.7, 0.05, 0.2)$ this ratio is 0.6 if $x_1 = 14$ and 0.8 if $x_1 = 15$.

5 Overall p -value

We use the sample space ordering proposed in the previous section to derive an overall p -value, denoted by Q , meant to be calculated when the trial has been terminated. Q is defined as the probability of observing under H_0 an outcome (m', x'_1, x') that is similar or more extreme than the outcome (m, x_1, x) actually observed in the trial. If the observed outcome is from a trial that stopped at the first stage outcomes with $x'_1 \geq x_1$ are more extreme, irrespective of their stopping stage, implying the overall p -value

$$Q = \Pr_{\pi_0}(X_1 \geq x_1).$$

If the observed outcome is from a trial that continued to the second stage, more extreme are outcomes from trials that stopped at the first stage with $x'_1 \geq u_1$ or continued to the

second stage with $\delta(x'_1, x'_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2)$, then

$$Q = \Pr_{\pi_0}(X_1 \geq u_1) + \sum_{x'_1=l_1+1}^{u_1-1} \Pr_{\pi_0}(X_1 = x'_1) \Pr_{\pi_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2) | X_1 = x'_1].$$

Since X_1 and X_2 follow binomial distribution, we can write the overall p -value as

$$Q = \begin{cases} 1 - B(x_1 - 1, n_1, \pi_0) & \text{if } m = 1 \\ 1 - B(u_1 - 1, n_1, \pi_0) + \sum_{x'_1=l_1+1}^{u_1-1} b(x'_1, n_1, \pi_0) \Pr_{\pi_0}(\Delta \geq \delta | x'_1) & \text{if } m = 2 \end{cases}$$

where $b(x, n, \pi)$ is the binomial probability mass function with x successes, n trials and success probability π , $\Delta = \delta(X_1, X_2)$ and $\delta = \delta(x_1, x_2)$.

We discuss in the following lines approaches to calculate the probability of $\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2)$ under H_0 , i.e., $\Pr_{\pi_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2)]$. For the $\delta(x_1, x_2)$ defined in (1), since we are working directly with the number of events (responses), this probability can easily be calculated as (let's call this *Method 1*)

$$\begin{aligned} & \Pr_{\pi_0}(\Delta \geq \delta | x'_1) \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2) | x'_1] \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[X - l(X_1) \geq x - l(x_1) | x'_1] \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[X_1 + X_2 - l(X_1) \geq x - l(x_1) | x'_1] \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[X_2 \geq x - l(x_1) + l(X_1) - X_1 | x'_1] \\ &= 1 - B[x - l(x_1) + l(x'_1) - x'_1 - 1, n_2(x'_1), \pi_0]. \end{aligned}$$

For the other two methods we use approximations. We make use of the fact that a p -value P is in general stochastically not smaller than a standard uniform variate, i.e.,

$$\Pr_{\pi_0}(P \leq \gamma) \leq \gamma, \gamma \in [0, 1].$$

Assuming that the first stage design is pre-fixed and is strictly followed, and that the first and the second stage data are from independent cohorts of patients, using the second stage p -value p_2 as the test statistic guarantees the *conditional invariance principle*⁴⁶. Conditional on the first stage data and second stage design, the distribution of p_2 under H_0 is not smaller than the uniform distribution. This implies that the type I error rate is controlled irrespective of the adaptation rule.

When using the $\delta(x_1, x_2)$ in (2) (Method 2), we approximate $\Pr_{\pi_0}(\Delta \geq \delta)$ as

$$\begin{aligned} Pr_{\pi_0}(\Delta \geq \delta|x'_1) &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2)|x'_1] \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[D(X_1) - P_2 \geq D(x_1) - p_2|x'_1] \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[P_2 \leq p_2 - D(x_1) + D(X_1)|x'_1] \\ &\approx \langle p_2 - D(x_1) + D(x'_1) \rangle_{[0,1]} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\langle \omega \rangle_{[0,1]} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } \omega < 0 \\ \omega & \text{if } 0 \leq \omega \leq 1 \\ 1 & \text{if } \omega > 1 \end{cases}$$

Another way of calculating $Pr_{\pi_0}(\Delta \geq \delta|x'_1)$ in Method 2, let's call it *Method 2v2*, is to use the fact that $p_2 = 1 - B[x_2 - 1, n_2(x_1), \pi_0]$ and the binomial quantile function, denoted by B_q , as it follows:

$$\begin{aligned} &\Pr_{\pi_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2)|x'_1] \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[P_2 \leq p_2 - D(x_1) + D(X_1)|x'_1] \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}\{1 - B[X_2 - 1, n_2(X_1), \pi_0] \leq p_2 - D(x_1) + D(X_1)\} \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}\{B[X_2 - 1, n_2(X_1), \pi_0] \geq 1 - p_2 + D(x_1) - D(X_1)\} \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}\{X_2 - 1 \geq B_q[1 - p_2 + D(x_1) - D(X_1), n_2(X_1), \pi_0]\} \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}\{X_2 \geq 1 + B_q[1 - p_2 + D(x_1) - D(X_1), n_2(X_1), \pi_0]\} \\ &= 1 - \\ &B\{B_q[1 - p_2 + D(x_1) - D(x'_1), n_2(x'_1), \pi_0], n_2(x'_1), \pi_0\} \end{aligned}$$

Finally, using the $\delta(x_1, x_2)$ in (3), *Method 3*, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr_{\pi_0}(\Delta \geq \delta|x'_1) &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2)|x'_1] \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[C(P_{1b}, P_2) \leq C(p_{1b}, p_2)|x'_1] \\ &= \Pr_{\pi_0}[P_2 \leq 1 - \Phi(z_b)|x'_1] \\ &\approx 1 - \Phi(z_b) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$z_b = \frac{w_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_{1b}) + w_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_2) - w'_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_{1b})}{w'_2}$$

See more details in the Appendix.

6 Point and interval estimation

We follow the approach discussed in Chapter 8 of⁴⁶. Exploiting the duality between confidence intervals (CI) and hypothesis tests, we construct the CI by considering all the null hypotheses

$$H_0^{\tilde{\pi}_0} : \pi \leq \tilde{\pi}_0, \text{ with } 0 \leq \tilde{\pi}_0 \leq 1.$$

Assuming that the overall p -value Q is monotone increasing in $\tilde{\pi}_0$ for all outcomes (m, x_1, x) , the region $\{\tilde{\pi}_0 : Q(\tilde{\pi}_0) = \Pr_{\tilde{\pi}_0}[(M, X_1, X) \succeq (m, x_1, x)] > \alpha\}$ is a one-sided $(1 - \alpha)100\%$ CI defined as $]\pi_L^\alpha; 1]$, where the lower bound π_L^α is the solution, in $\tilde{\pi}_0$, of the equation $Q(\tilde{\pi}_0) = \alpha$. That is, the CI is a set of $\tilde{\pi}_0$ for which H_0 is not rejected.

As the point estimate we take the lower bound of the 50% one-sided CI, i.e., $\hat{\pi} = \pi_L^{0.5}$, which is an approximate median unbiased estimator. Similar estimators have been proposed for classical oncology two-stage GSDs by¹⁴ and¹⁸, which are applicable only if n_2 is a constant for all x_1 .

As mentioned before, in order to this estimation technique to work it is necessary that the overall p -value Q as function of response probability π be monotone increasing for $\pi \in [0, 1]$. We checked the monotonicity of $Q(\pi)$ numerically for all 34 designs listed in⁸, for all possible outcomes and π ranging from 0 to 1 by increments of 0.01. We found that Methods 2 and 3 are monotone in all designs. Method 1 is monotone, except for 4 designs when $\pi \geq 0.8$. In the case of non-monotonicity, a conservative solution may be found using the cumulative maximum of $Q(\pi)$, i.e., $Q_{cm}(\pi) = \max\{Q(\pi') : \pi' \leq \pi\}$.

We give more details on how the estimation is done for each of the three methods in the Appendix.

7 Illustrative example

Suppose that a Phase II trial testing the activity of an anti-cancer agent was conducted using the design given in Table 1. Suppose further that at the interim analysis it was found that eight out of 20 patients responded to the treatment, leading to the decision to proceed with the trial to the second (final) stage. Therefore, 39 additional patients were recruited and treated, of which 18 were responsive. With a total of 26 responders out of 59 patients at the end of trial, the decision according to the design's decision rule was to reject the null. Calculating the overall p -value using the proposed approach, methods 1, 2, 2v2 and 3, we get the values 0.00261, 0.00360, 0.00315 and 0.00261, respectively. As it can be seen, all the p -values are less than the significance

level $\alpha = 0.05$, meaning that with the proposed methods we also reject the null hypothesis. With the null hypothesis rejected, one would be interested in getting the response rate estimate to possibly use it for planing further trials. If we would ignore the adaptive nature of the design and employ the fixed-sample maximum likelihood estimator, the point estimate would be 0.44068. The point estimates obtained using the proposed approach are 0.42264, 0.41367, 0.41337 and 0.41411 respectively for the methods 1, 2, 2v2 and 3. The corresponding 95% one-sided CIs are $[0.29561; 1]$, $[0.29105; 1]$, $[0.27918; 1]$ and $[0.29379; 1]$.

8 Numerical study

We did an extensive numerical study to evaluate various aspects of the proposed methods. We computed, for all designs in ⁸, the overall p -value to see how it behaves for the three methods, as well as to check whether it is consistent with the original decision rule. The computation was for all possible outcomes, with values of π_0 varying from 0 to 1 by 0.01 for each. We then did a simulation study to assess the performance of the proposed estimator using the three methods. The performance of the point estimate was quantified in terms of bias and root mean square error (RMSE), and the performance of the interval estimate was quantified by the coverage probability and mean of the lower bound. We calculated, in addition, the type I error and power using the original decision rule and using the overall p -value from the proposed methods.

Bias was defined as $\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (\hat{\pi}_t - \pi)$ and RMSE as the square root of $\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T (\hat{\pi}_t - \pi)^2$, where T is the total number of simulated trials, $\hat{\pi}$ the estimated response probability and π the response probability under which trials were simulated. The coverage probability was computed as the proportion of trials in which the $(1 - \alpha)100\%$ CI contained the true response rate π , i.e., proportion of trials in which the lower bound of the CI is less than π . The type I error was calculated as the proportion of trials simulated under $\pi = \pi_0$ in which H_0 was rejected, and the power calculated similarly but for trials simulated under $\pi = \pi_1$.

For comparison purposes we included the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) for fixed-sample designs, which we believe is more likely to be employed when analysing data from adaptive designs for which no specific estimation methods are available. When applying this estimator, we ignored the adaptive nature of the design and we did estimation as if the data were from a fixed-sample (single-stage) design. Therefore, the MLE is the sample proportion of the pooled data. We didn't include the estimators proposed

for classical GSDs mentioned above. Their formulae are based on the fact that the second stage sample size is predefined and constant, therefore, they wouldn't be applicable here without modification. We used two versions of MLE, one that uses all trial data, $\hat{\pi}_p = [x_1 + x_2]/[n_1 + n_2(x_1)]$, and the other that uses the first stage data only, $\hat{\pi}_{p1} = x_1/n_1$. The reason for including $\hat{\pi}_{p1}$ is that since it is unbiased, it will serve as benchmark for comparison with respect to RMSE, i.e., a new estimator would not be desirable if it would be outperformed by $\hat{\pi}_{p1}$ in terms of RMSE. We denote the estimated response probability by $\hat{\pi}_{m1}$ for Method 1, $\hat{\pi}_{m2}$ for Method 2, $\hat{\pi}_{m2v2}$ for Method 2v2, and $\hat{\pi}_{m3}$ for Method 3. The simulation were done for two designs of⁸, one with a moderate π_1 , $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.2, 0.4, 0.05, 0.1, 20)$, we call this design 1, and the other (design 2) with relatively high π_1 , $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.4, 0.6, 0.05, 0.1, 22)$. For both designs we varied, in the simulated trials, the true response probability π from 0 to 1 by increments of 0.01. For each scenario 50 000 simulations were run.

We implemented all the methodology described above in the statistical programming language R⁴⁰. The code and datasets containing all designs listed in⁸ are available from the authors upon request.

9 Results

Figure 1 shows plots of overall p -value for all possible values of x when $x_1 = 8$ and $x_1 = 11$ in designs 1 and 2, respectively. It can be seen that, as expected, all methods are consistent with design's decision rule. Results from simulation study in Table 2 reveal that type I error rate and power of Methods 1 and 2v2 are equal to those of design's original decision rule, which are in turn very close to the nominal levels. Methods 2 and 3 are conservative, as their type I error rate and power are lower compared to other methods.

Table 2. Type I error and power based on design's original decision rule (Orig.) and on the three proposed methods (Met.), from 50000 simulation runs. The two first rows are for design 1, $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.2, 0.4, 0.05, 0.1, 20)$, and the last two for the design 2, $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.4, 0.6, 0.05, 0.1, 22)$.

	Decision rule				
	Orig.	Met. 1	Met. 2	Met.2v2	Met. 3
Type I	0.0503	0.0503	0.0430	0.0503	0.0430
Power	0.9002	0.9002	0.8877	0.9002	0.8877
Type I	0.0492	0.0492	0.0421	0.0492	0.0428
Power	0.8990	0.8990	0.8884	0.8990	0.8892

(a) Design 1

(b) Design 2

Figure 1. Plot of overall p -value (Q) as function of the total number of responses (x). Figure (a) is of the design $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.2, 0.4, 0.05, 0.1, 20)$ with $x_1 = 5$, and (b) of $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.4, 0.6, 0.05, 0.1, 22)$ with $x_1 = 10$. Both are cases where the trial continues to second stage. The vertical line represents the minimum total number of responses necessary to reject H_0 using design's decision rule.

Simulation results on bias and RMSE of the estimators for values of π ranging from 0 to 1 are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3, respectively. Table 3 shows the results of simulations under H_1 ($\pi = \pi_1$), and, in addition to bias and RMSE, it shows the mean and the first, second and third quartiles of the estimates, and the coverage probability and the mean lower bound of the one-sided $(1 - \alpha)100\%$ CI. The same results for simulations under $\pi = \pi_1 + 0.1$ are shown in Table 4. The behaviour of the estimators change depending on whether the true response rate (π) is close to or far from the hypothesized one (π_1). Taking a closer

look at the Figure 2 we can see that, except the first stage sample proportion ($\hat{\pi}_{p1}$) which is unbiased as expected, all estimators are negatively mean biased for values of π around π_0 . When the true response rate is close to π_1 , the estimators of the proposed methods ($\hat{\pi}_{m1}$, $\hat{\pi}_{m2}$, $\hat{\pi}_{m2v2}$ and $\hat{\pi}_{m3}$) are almost unbiased, while the fixed sample MLE ($\hat{\pi}_p$) shows positive bias. As π approaches 1, the proposed estimators become more and more negatively biased, while the bias of $\hat{\pi}_p$ approaches 0. Among the proposed estimators, $\hat{\pi}_{m2v2}$ behaves slightly different, as π moves from π_0 to 1, it is the first to attain mean bias that is closest to zero, which happens just after π_1 . Regarding RMSE (see Figure 3), the proposed estimators also outperform $\hat{\pi}_p$ for values of π around π_1 . Their RMSE is also lower than that of $\hat{\pi}_{p1}$.

From Table 3 we see that under H_1 the simulation mean and median are similar, and they are relatively lower in the proposed estimator as compared to $\hat{\pi}_p$. The one-sided CIs have good coverage probabilities for all the proposed methods, with values that are not less than the nominal level (95%). The mean of the lower bound of CIs are similar across the proposed methods. The simulation done assuming $\pi = \pi_1 + 0.1$ (Table 4) showed similar results.

Table 3. Performance measures of estimator under H_1 (i.e., $\pi = \pi_1$). The measures are the mean, median (Med.), mean bias (M.Bias), RMSE, first and third quartiles (Q.), and the coverage probability (Cov.P) and mean of lower bound (M.LB) of the one-sided $(1 - \alpha)100\%$ confidence interval. The first group of rows are for the design 1, $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.2, 0.4, 0.05, 0.1, 20)$, and the other for 2 $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.4, 0.6, 0.05, 0.1, 22)$. A total of 50000 trials were simulated for each design.

	True response rate: $\pi = \pi_1$				
	$\hat{\pi}_p$	$\hat{\pi}_{m1}$	$\hat{\pi}_{m2}$	$\hat{\pi}_{m2v2}$	$\hat{\pi}_{m3}$
Mean	0.4126	0.3974	0.3966	0.4008	0.3968
Med.	0.4068	0.3978	0.3897	0.3975	0.3887
M.Bias	0.0126	-0.0026	-0.0034	0.0008	-0.0032
RMSE	0.1052	0.0962	0.0965	0.0956	0.0964
1 st Q.	0.3559	0.3385	0.3414	0.3486	0.3408
3 rd Q.	0.5000	0.4648	0.4677	0.4682	0.4677
Cov.P		0.9785	0.9785	0.9785	0.9785
M.LB		0.2685	0.2678	0.2660	0.2681
Mean	0.6057	0.5941	0.5933	0.5991	0.5935
Med.	0.6027	0.5983	0.5915	0.5976	0.5904
M.Bias	0.0057	-0.0059	-0.0067	-0.0009	-0.0065
RMSE	0.0976	0.0911	0.0912	0.0920	0.0911
1 st Q.	0.5556	0.5502	0.5471	0.5524	0.5483
3 rd Q.	0.6575	0.6422	0.6383	0.6599	0.6400
Cov.P		0.9742	0.9742	0.9742	0.9742
M.LB		0.4723	0.4716	0.4677	0.4718

(a) Design 1

(a) Design 1

(b) Design 2

(b) Design 2

Figure 2. Mean bias of estimators. Design 1 is defined by $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.2, 0.4, 0.05, 0.1, 20)$, and 2 by $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.4, 0.6, 0.05, 0.1, 22)$. For each value of π 50000 trials were simulated. The vertical line represents $\pi = \pi_1$.

Figure 3. RMSE of estimators. Design 1 is defined by $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.2, 0.4, 0.05, 0.1, 20)$, and 2 by $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.4, 0.6, 0.05, 0.1, 22)$. For each value of π 50000 trials were simulated. The vertical line represents $\pi = \pi_1$.

10 Discussion

In this paper we have discussed and proposed sample space orderings for oncology Phase II adaptive two-stage designs with binary endpoint. Overall p -value and point and interval estimation were derived from these sample space orderings. Although for some values of true response probability our methods don't show improvement over the fixed sample MLE, they are preferable because they consistently outperform the MLE when the true response probability is in the neighbourhood of values that are equal to or greater than the response probability under the alternative hypothesis. It is in this region where the estimation becomes

particularly important since the null hypothesis would likely have been rejected and the treatment effect estimate needed to plan later Phase III trials. In this region the MLE shows high positive bias and higher RMSE while our methods are either unbiased or negatively biased with smaller RMSE. In general, as opposed to the fixed sample MLE, our proposed methods do not overestimate the response probability. This is seen by the fact that for values of true response rate ranging from 0 to 1, they are either unbiased or negatively biased. Overestimation of treatment effect in Phase II trials has been acknowledged in the literature as one of the reasons for high failure rate of drugs in Phase III. For example,⁵² showed an evidence that supports the need to,

Table 4. Performance measures of estimator under $\pi = \pi_1 + 0.1$. The measures are the mean, median (Med.), mean bias (M.Bias), RMSE, first and third quartiles (Q.), and the coverage probability (Cov.P) and mean of lower bound (M.LB) of the one-sided $(1 - \alpha)100\%$ confidence interval. The first group of rows are for the design 1, $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.2, 0.4, 0.05, 0.1, 20)$, and the other for 2 $(\pi_0, \pi_1, \alpha, \beta, n_1) = (0.4, 0.6, 0.05, 0.1, 22)$. A total of 50000 trials were simulated for each design.

	True response rate: $\pi = \pi_1 + 0.1$				
	$\hat{\pi}_p$	$\hat{\pi}_{m1}$	$\hat{\pi}_{m2}$	$\hat{\pi}_{m2v2}$	$\hat{\pi}_{m3}$
Mean	0.5265	0.4971	0.4970	0.4931	0.4971
Med.	0.5085	0.4754	0.4754	0.4754	0.4754
M.Bias	0.0265	-0.0029	-0.0030	-0.0069	-0.0029
RMSE	0.0950	0.0885	0.0884	0.0926	0.0883
1 st Q.	0.4746	0.4434	0.4410	0.4283	0.4425
3 rd Q.	0.6000	0.5737	0.5737	0.5737	0.5737
Cov.P	0.9785	0.9785	0.9785	0.9785	0.9785
M.LB	0.3369	0.3353	0.3319	0.3369	0.3369
Mean	0.7248	0.6978	0.6980	0.6925	0.6980
Med.	0.7273	0.6980	0.6994	0.6994	0.6982
M.Bias	0.0248	-0.0022	-0.0020	-0.0075	-0.0020
RMSE	0.0808	0.0726	0.0722	0.0786	0.0721
1 st Q.	0.6761	0.6522	0.6502	0.6436	0.6509
3 rd Q.	0.7727	0.7462	0.7462	0.7462	0.7462
Cov.P	0.9792	0.9792	0.9792	0.9792	0.9792
M.LB	0.5513	0.5488	0.5416	0.5515	0.5515

and proposed methods to, discount the Phase II estimate of treatment effect when it is used to plan Phase III trial sample size.

Although our methods were built on top of⁸ design, they can easily be extended to other similar designs with pre-specified adaptation rules. One example are the adaptive designs by^{9,10}. Further, some of our proposed approaches (methods 2 and 3) remain valid even if the adaptation rule is not pre-specified, meaning that they can be applied for flexible designs.

Declaration of conflicting interests

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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Appendix

Details of Method 3

Let's first show how $p_{1b}(x_1)$ is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned}
A(p_{1b}(x_1)) &= D(x_1) \\
\Leftrightarrow 1 - \Phi \left\{ \frac{\Phi^{-1}(1-c) - w_1 \Phi^{-1}[1 - p_{1b}(x_1)]}{w_2} \right\} &= D(x_1) \\
\Leftrightarrow \frac{\Phi^{-1}(1-c) - w_1 \Phi^{-1}[1 - p_{1b}(x_1)]}{w_2} &= \Phi^{-1}[1 - D(x_1)] \\
\Leftrightarrow \Phi^{-1}[1 - p_{1b}(x_1)] &= \frac{\Phi^{-1}(1-c) - w_2 \Phi^{-1}[1 - D(x_1)]}{w_1} \\
\Leftrightarrow 1 - p_{1b}(x_1) &= \Phi \left\{ \frac{\Phi^{-1}(1-c) - w_2 \Phi^{-1}[1 - D(x_1)]}{w_1} \right\} \\
\Leftrightarrow p_{1b}(x_1) &= 1 - \Phi \left\{ \frac{\Phi^{-1}(1-c) - w_2 \Phi^{-1}[1 - D(x_1)]}{w_1} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

We have that

$$\begin{aligned}
\delta(x'_1, x'_2) &\geq \delta(x_1, x_2) \\
\Leftrightarrow \delta[p_{1b}(x'_1), p_2(x'_2)] &\geq \delta[p_{1b}(x_1), p_2(x_2)] \\
\Leftrightarrow 1 - C(p'_{1b}, p'_2) &\geq 1 - C(p_{1b}, p_2) \\
\Leftrightarrow C(p'_{1b}, p'_2) &\leq C(p_{1b}, p_2) \\
\Leftrightarrow 1 - \Phi [w'_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_{1b}) + w'_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_2)] &\leq \\
1 - \Phi [w_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_{1b}) + w_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_2)] & \\
\Leftrightarrow \Phi [w'_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_{1b}) + w'_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_2)] &\geq \\
\Phi [w_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_{1b}) + w_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_2)] & \\
\Leftrightarrow w'_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_{1b}) + w'_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_2) &\geq \\
w_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_{1b}) + w_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_2) & \\
\Leftrightarrow \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_2) &\geq \\
\frac{w_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_{1b}) + w_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_2) - w'_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_{1b})}{w'_2} & \\
\Leftrightarrow 1 - p'_2 &\geq \\
\Phi \left[\frac{w_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_{1b}) + w_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_2) - w'_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_{1b})}{w'_2} \right] & \\
\Leftrightarrow p'_2 &\leq \\
1 - \Phi \left[\frac{w_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_{1b}) + w_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_2) - w'_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_{1b})}{w'_2} \right] &
\end{aligned}$$

Note that some of steps above are only valid because Φ is a continuous and monotone increasing function.

Details on point and interval estimation

Let π_0 be the response probability under the design's original null hypothesis H_0 , we denote by $\tilde{\pi}_0$ the response probability under all null hypotheses we consider when searching for point and interval estimates, with $0 \leq \tilde{\pi}_0 \leq 1$. Then the

overall p -value to search for the estimates is defined as

$$Q(\tilde{\pi}_0) = \begin{cases} 1 - B(x_1 - 1, n_1, \tilde{\pi}_0) & \text{if } m = 1 \\ 1 - B(u_1 - 1, n_1, \tilde{\pi}_0) + \sum_{x'_1=l_1+1}^{u_1-1} b(x'_1, n_1, \tilde{\pi}_0) \Pr_{\tilde{\pi}_0}(\Delta \geq \delta | x'_1) & \text{if } m = 2 \end{cases}$$

where $\Pr_{\tilde{\pi}_0}(\Delta \geq \delta) = \Pr_{\tilde{\pi}_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2)]$ is calculated for the different methods as follows. For the Method 1,

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Pr_{\tilde{\pi}_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2) | X_1 = x'_1] \\
&= 1 - B[x - l(x_1) + l(x'_1) - x'_1 - 1, n_2(x'_1), \tilde{\pi}_0].
\end{aligned}$$

For the Method 2

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Pr_{\tilde{\pi}_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2) | X_1 = x'_1] \\
&\approx \langle \tilde{p}_2 - D(x_1) + D(x'_1) \rangle_{[0,1]}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\tilde{p}_2 = 1 - B[x_2 - 1, n_2(x_1), \tilde{\pi}_0]$.

For the Method 2v2

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Pr_{\tilde{\pi}_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2) | X_1 = x'_1] \\
&= 1 - B\{B_q[1 - p_2 + D(x_1) - D(x'_1), n_2(x'_1), \pi_0], n_2(x'_1), \tilde{\pi}_0\}
\end{aligned}$$

with $p_2 = 1 - B[x_2 - 1, n_2(x_1), \pi_0]$.

And for the Method 3

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Pr_{\tilde{\pi}_0}[\delta(X_1, X_2) \geq \delta(x_1, x_2) | X_1 = x'_1] \\
&\approx 1 - \Phi \left[\frac{w_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p_{1b}) + w_2 \Phi^{-1}(1 - \tilde{p}_2) - w'_1 \Phi^{-1}(1 - p'_{1b})}{w'_2} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

where $\tilde{p}_2 = 1 - B[x_2 - 1, n_2(x_1), \tilde{\pi}_0]$.